

BIO-ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE ESTIMATION OF MYCOPHENOLATE MOFETIL IN HUMAN PLASMA BY RP-HPLC METHOD

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ABSTRACT

To develop a new rapid and precise bio-analytical method using RP-HPLC with an appropriate internal standard for the estimation of mycophenolate mofetil with simple and effective sample preparation. Liquid-liquid extraction procedure was employed for the sample preparation. Enable C8 reverse phase column with the mobile phase of phosphate buffer (pH 3.5) adjusted with ortho phosphoric acid and acetonitrile:methanol (90:10) in the ratio of 60:40% v/v and the detection was carried out at 254 nm. The retention time of Mycophenolate mofetil and Amlodipine (IS) was found to be 6.7 and 8.6 respectively, which is highly advantageous. Over the concentration range of 200–1000 ng/ml the graph showed linearity and within the limit of ($r > 0.999$). Validated analytical method was based on the parameters selectivity, accuracy, precision, repeatability, linearity, LOD, LOQ, and the suitability of the system. Validation analysis showed selectivity test, LLOD, LOQ were within the range. Percent accuracy from 99.4% to 100.5% for intraday studies and 99.7% to 101.07% for interday studies and precision 6.65% to 7.52% for intraday studies and 6.65% to 7.52% for interday studies. The study was also extended to know the suitable matrix for the drug. Hence the method developed can be employed for therapeutic drug monitoring, bioequivalence and bioavailability studies of mycophenolate mofetil.

Key words: RP-HPLC, Mycophenolate mofetil, Liquid-liquid extraction, human plasma, Therapeutic drug monitoring and bioequivalence.

INTRODUCTION

Bio-analysis is defined as the Quantitative determination of drugs and their metabolites in biological fluids. It is widely applied to study in areas of human clinical pharmacology and non-human pharmacology/toxicology. Bioanalytical method employed for the quantitative determination of drugs and their metabolites in biological fluids, plays a significant role in the evaluation and interpretation of bioequivalence, pharmacokinetic (PK), and toxicokinetic studies. The major bio-analytical services are method development, method validation and sample analysis (method application). Whatever way the analysis is done it must be checked to see whether it does and what it is purposed to do; i.e it must be validated. Each step in the method must be investigated to determine the extent to which environment, matrix or procedural variables can affect the estimation of analyte in the matrix from the time of collection up to the time of analysis. Both HPLC and LCMS-MS can be used for the bioanalysis of drugs in plasma. Each of the instruments has its own merits and demerits. HPLC coupled with UV, PDA or fluorescence detector can be used for estimation of many compounds but it does not give the high sensitivity as required by some of the potent, low dose drugs and lacks selectivity.

Typical choices of sample preparation techniques useful in bioanalysis

- Dilution followed by injection
- Solid Phase extraction (off line/online)
- Protein precipitation
- Filtration
- Liquid-liquid extraction
- Protein removal by equilibrium dialysis or ultrafiltration
- Restricted access media
- Solid-supported liquid-liquid extraction
- Monolithic columns
- Immunoaffinity extraction
- Combinations of all the above

The technique used here is Liquid-liquid extraction

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Chemicals and solvents used for estimation-

- | | | |
|-------------------|---|---------------------------|
| • HPLC Water | - | Qualigens, Mumbai, India. |
| • Acetonitrile | - | Rankem, Mumbai, India. |
| • Methanol | - | Himedia, Mumbai, India. |
| • Distilled water | - | Double Distilled water. |

- Potassium Di-hydrogen phosphate - Analytical grade, SD fine chemicals, Mumbai.
- Orthophosphoric acid - SD fine chem. Ltd, Mumbai.

Instruments used:

- ✓ Elico pH meter LI 127.
- ✓ Shimadzu LC-20 AT HPLC.
- ✓ SPD-M20A Prominence diode array detector.
- ✓ Shimadzu 1700 LC-UV Spectrophotometer.
- ✓ Sonica ultrasonic cleaner.
- ✓ Solvent filtration unit – Millipore.
- ✓ Shimadzu electronic balance AY 220.
- ✓ Ultra cooling centrifuge – Remi, India

Selection of Wavelength-

An uv spectrum of 100 µg/ml mycophenolate mofetil in methanol was recorded by scanning in the range of 200 nm to 400 nm. A wavelength which gives good response for the drugs to be detected is to be selected. From the uv spectrum a wavelength of 254 nm was selected. Mycophenolate mofetil showed optimal absorbance at this wavelength.

Selection of chromatographic method

Selection of proper chromatographic method depends on the nature of the sample or its properties like ionic/ionizable/neutral character, its molecular weight and solubility. The drug selected for the present study was polar in nature hence, reverse phase HPLC or ion-pair or ion-exchange chromatography method must be used. Because of its simplicity and suitability for initial separations reverse phase method was selected.

Standard solution:

100µg/ml of mycophenolate mofetil was prepared by dissolving in 10 ml of HPLC grade methanol.

Equipment:

- System : Shimadzu gradient HPLC
- Pump : LC-20AT prominence solvent delivery system
- Detector : SPD-M20A prominence diode array detector
- Injector : Rheodyne 7725i with 20µl loop

Selection of internal standard

Based upon polarity and solubility, albendazole, piroxicam, lamivudine, ibuprofen and amlodipine were selected and chromatographed along with the standard drug. The elution time of amlodipine was 8.6 min. The peak of amlodipine was symmetric and well resolved from the peak of the mycophenolate mofetil. Hence, for the present study amlodipine was selected as the internal standard

Fixed Chromatographic Conditions

Stationary phase	: Enable C8 column
Mobile phase	: Solvent A – Phosphate buffer pH adjusted to 3.5 (with orthophosphoric acid) Solvent B – Acetonitrile:Methanol (90 : 10)
Solvent ratio	: 60 : 40 (A: B)
Detection Wavelength	: 254 nm
Flow rate	: 1.5 ml/min
Sample size	: 20 µl
Needle wash	: HPLC grade water
Temperature	: Room temperature (25°C)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC METHOD

A bio-analytical method was developed for Mycophenolate mofetil an immunosuppressant. The chromatographic conditions were stabilized in order to provide a good performance of the assay. The standard and internal standard solutions were prepared and chromatograms were recorded. This project proposes a method for the determination of mycophenolate mofetil by liquid-liquid extraction using RP-HPLC.

Chromatographic separation of standard Mycophenolate mofetil:

The chromatogram of mycophenolate mofetil was recorded alone and shown in fig 1. The standard solution which contains internal standard amlodipine was injected with the developed chromatographic conditions, and the chromatograms were recorded and shown in fig 2

Fig1:DRUG AT 100mcg

Table 1:Drug with Rt and their internal standard

S. No	Method	Retention time of Drugs (min)	
		Mycophenolate mofetil	Internal Standard (Amlodipine)
1	HPLC	6.803	8.660
2		6.842	8.687
3		6.860	8.672
4		6.793	8.664
5		6.792	8.667

The chromatogram of the blank plasma was recorded at the fixed chromatographic conditions and shown in figure (Fig 13).

Fig: 3 - Chromatogram of blank plasma

Various solvents were used for extraction of mycophenolate mofetil in human plasma. But, out of all solvents acetonitrile-methanol (80:20) mixture was proved to be good because of its maximum percentage recovery. The percentage recoveries were calculated and shown in table . The retention time for mycophenolate mofetil and internal standard (Amlodipine) were 6.8 and 8.9 minutes

Table 4: Recovery study of mycophenolate mofetil

Level	Conc. of drug added (ng/ml)	Amt. of drug recovered from plasma (ng/ml)			% Recovery		
		Methanol	ACN	ACN and methanol mixture	Methanol	ACN	ACN and Methanol mixture
I	50	32.4	34.4	48.2	64.8	68.8	96.4
II	100	74.6	78.2	97.2	74.6	78.2	97.2
III	150	121.4	118.5	147.4	80.9	78.9	98.2

Comparison of matrix:

To study the appropriate matrix for estimation was carried out using plasma and serum. An aliquot of drug along with plasma and serum are taken separately, vortexed and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatant liquid was collected and the sample was analysed for five different days, from which plasma was found to be more stable compared to the serum.

Hence plasma was selected for the further studies. Chromatogram with drug and serum are shown

Plasma and drug

serum and drug

Comparison of plasma and serum (Inter day)

COMPONENTS	PEAK AREA OF COMPONENT	PEAK AREA OF DRUG
DAY 1(400ng/ml)		
PLASMA	2547861	615482
SERUM	2368456	596847
DAY 2(400ng/ml)		

PLASMA SERUM	2463246 1985547	609984 478697
DAY 3(400ng/ml)		
PLASMA SERUM	2427843 1798784	601889 438451
DAY 4(400ng/ml)		
PLASMA SERUM	2609874 1698784	598761 426911
DAY 5(400ng/ml)		
PLASMA SERUM	2469965 1522473	594412 405596

Intra-day studies: In this plasma concentration 200-1000 ng/ml were injected six times and mean peak area was calculated separately for each concentration and from that accuracy and precision percentage RSD values were calculated and shown in (Table 6)

Table 6: Accuracy and precision studies of mycophenolate mofetil (Intraday)

Sl.no	Conc. of drug (ng/ml)	Mean peak area	Accuracy (%)	RSD** (%)
1	200	30268	100.5	7.52
2	400	61820	99.8	6.96
3	600	92516	99.4	6.65

**Average of six determinations.

Inter-day studies: In this the plasma concentrations of 200-1000 ng/ml were injected into HPLC six times in three different days and mean peak areas were calculated and from that accuracy and precision percentage RSD were calculated and shown in (Table 7). The percentage relative standard deviation of precision for mycophenolate mofetil was less than 15% for the bioanalytical study. The results obtained were within limits.

Acceptance criteria: The percentage RSD value should be less than 15% for bio-analytical study.

: Accuracy and precision studies of mycophenolate mofetil (Interday)

Sl.no	Conc. of drug (ng/ml)	Mean peak area	Accuracy (%)	RSD** (%)
1	200	31584	101.07	7.88
2	400	60248	99.7	6.39
3	600	94662	100.4	7.49

**Average of six determinations.

Linearity and range:

This method proved to be linear between ng/ml of mycophenolate mofetil in human plasma, with a typical calibration curve of correlation equation $y = 0.1535x + 0.0274$, correlation coefficient > 0.999 shown in

Calibration standards peak area

Concentration (ng/ml)	Peak area of drug	Peak area of IS	Response factor
20	30268	39738	0.762
40	61820		1.554
60	92516		2.329
80	128175		3.258
100	159655		4.072

Fig 4 200 µg/ml

Fig 5 400µg/ml

Fig 6 600µg/ml

Fig 7 800µg/ml

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The method demonstrated relative recoveries with acceptable relative standard deviation. The lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) for mycophenolate mofetil was found to be nanograms lesser than unity. Hence the developed method is sensitive for the estimation of Mycophenolate mofetil in trace amounts.

Peak purity studies, with peak purity index values closer to unity reveals that the method developed was specific for the estimation of Mycophenolate mofetil in blood and other biological fluids.

Conclusion

From the current work it was finally concluded that the developed RP-HPLC method in human plasma was found to be very simple, reliable and selective for providing satisfactory accuracy and precision. The method developed was found to be rapid with the evident of short retention time. Furthermore the method has been shown to be specific and selective by peak purity study. The study was also extended to know the suitable matrix for the drug. Hence the method developed can be used for therapeutic drug monitoring, bioequivalence and bioavailability study of mycophenolate mofetil.

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